

Original Research Article

Estimation of Clinical and Immunological Failure of First Line Antiretroviral Treatment in King Koti ART Centre, Hyderabad, Telangana

Dr. Deepak Pandharpurkar¹, Dr. Gudikandula Krishna²,
Dr. G. Rasheeda Begum³, P. Mallikarjun⁴

¹Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Centre of Excellence, Gandhi Hospital, Secundrabad

²Research Fellow (Non Clinical), Centre of Excellence Gandhi Hospital, Secundrabad

³Senior Medical Officer, ART Center, Kingkoti, Hyderabad

⁴Data Analyst, Centre of Excellence Gandhi Hospital, Secundrabad

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepak Pandharpurkar

ABSTRACT

Introduction: The treatment outcomes under national antiretroviral therapy (ART) programme are being evaluated in ART centers in the country. We carried out this study to analyze the impact of first line antiretroviral therapy in HIV infected patients attending free ART. The main objective of this work is to determine the clinical and immunological failure rate at first-line treatment.

Methods: We have conducted a prospective, observational cohort study of patients living with HIV who had suspected failure of first line ART using data collected under programmatic condition. Four hundred and three patients from ART center King Koti, Hyderabad from January 1, 2017 to December 2018 was taken in the study.

Results: Between January 2017 to December 2018, 403 patients were registered in the ART clinic. Of these, 318 (52.6%) were on ART. Females accounted for 48% and males constitute 51%. Patients had a mean age of 37 ± 12 yr, Median CD4 count was 560 cells/ μ l (IQR: 289-734). 13 patients (4.2%) were in clinical stage 3 and 10 (8.24%) in clinical stage 4 for HIV infection according to the WHO classification. CD4 T-cells counts were between 4 and 1591 cells/mm³ with 174 patients (56%) with CD4 count below 500 cells/mm³.

Conclusion: The rate of immunological failure rate of first-line antiretroviral treatment of patients under treatment in King Koti, Hyderabad is 7.5% for the year 2017 and 18.

Key Words: Antiretroviral therapy, Clinical failure, Immunological failure

INTRODUCTION

Total number of individuals living with HIV (PLHIV) in India was evaluated at 21.17 lakhs (17.11 lakhs- 26.49 lakhs) in 2015 contrasted and 22.26 lakhs (18.00 lakhs-27.85 lakhs) in 2007. Children (< 15 years) represented 6.54%, while women contributed around two fifth (40.5%) of absolute HIV diseases. Unified Andhra Pradesh and Telangana have the most elevated evaluated number of PLHIV (3.95

lakhs) trailed by Maharashtra (3.01 lakhs), Karnataka (1.99 lakhs), Gujarat (1.66 lakhs), Bihar (1.51 lakhs) and Uttar Pradesh (1.50 lakhs). These seven States together record for 66% (64.4%) of all out evaluated PLHIV. Rajasthan (1.03 lakhs), Tamil Nadu (1.43 lakhs) and West Bengal (1.29 lakhs) are different States with assessed PLHIV quantities of 1 lakh or more. In India, the assessed number of new HIV infections in 2015 were around 86 (56-129) thousand.

Manipur has shown the highest estimated adult HIV prevalence (1.15%), trailed by Mizoram (0.80%), Nagaland (0.78%), Andhra Pradesh and Telangana (0.66%), Karnataka (0.45%), Gujarat (0.42%) and Goa (0.40%). Other than these States, Maharashtra, Chandigarh, Tripura and Tamil Nadu have shown an estimated adult HIV predominance more noteworthy than the national pervasiveness (0.26%), while Odisha, Bihar, Sikkim, Delhi, Rajasthan and West Bengal have demonstrated an expected grown-up HIV commonness in the scope of 0.21– 0.25%. Every other State/UTs have adult HIV pervasiveness underneath 0.20%.^[1]

The basic principle for first-line ART for treatment naïve adult and adolescent patients is to use a triple drug combination from two different classes of ARVs. The first-line ART essentially comprises of a NRTI backbone, preferably Non-Thymidine (Tenofovir plus Lamivudine) and one NNRTI, preferably EFV. Based on the evidence supporting better efficacy and fewer side effects, it is now recommended that all PLHIV with HIV-1 infection be initiated on a regimen consisting of TLE

The objective of this work is to determine the clinical and immunological failure rate at first-line treatment in King Koti Hospital Secunderabad, Telangana.

METHODS

Study design and population

We have conducted a prospective, observational cohort study of patients living with HIV who had suspected failure of first line ART using data collected under programmatic condition. Four hundred and three patients from ART center King Koti, Hyderabad from January 1, 2017 to December 2018 was taken in the study. At 6th month of antiretroviral treatment, 318 patients were received for the assessments and analyzes of the parameters remaining patients were left out from the treatment. The first-line treatment used for all patients was a combination of

Zidovudine (ZDV), Lamivudine (3TC) and Nevirapine (NVP) and Tenofovir Lamivudine (3TC) and Nevirapine (NVP) which is the most available combination in the ART centers India.

Data collection and analysis

Statistic and clinical data of all patients living with HIV was recorded in patient documents. The clinical information that was routinely gathered for every patient, including treatment and investigation reports, was entered into an excel database. A full-time data manager routinely administered information section for precision and culmination. Information from all patients associated with first -line failure between January 1, 2017 to December 2018 were incorporated into the investigations. Descriptive statistics for measurements were utilized to investigate the information of these patients utilizing SPSS.

Operational Definitions

Clinical failure to treatment is based on the reoccurrence of opportunistic infections and/or progression to a higher clinical stage after the start of treatment, as well as the lost of weight of patient in a context without stress problem and reconstruction syndrome.

Immunological failure to treatment is defined by the absence of increased CD4 T-cells count despite effective ARV therapy for at least 6 months. This is seen more frequently in patients with initially low CD4 cell counts. As a general rule, a CD4 count below 200 cells/mm³ is an indicator of immunological failure.

Virological failure to treatment is defined as a persistence VL greater than 1000 copies of RNA/ml 6 months after the start of treatment.^[2-4]

RESULTS

Between January 2017 to December 2018, 403 patients were registered in the ART clinic. Of these, 318 (52.6%) were on ART. The baseline characteristics of these patients are shown in the Table 1. Females

accounted for 48% and males constitute 51%. Patients had a mean age of 37 ± 12 yr, Median CD4 count was 560 cells/ μ l (IQR: 289-734). 13 patients (4.2%) were in clinical stage 3 and 10 (8.24%) in clinical stage 4 for HIV infection according to the WHO classification. [5] CD4 T-cells counts were between 4 and 1591 cells/mm³ with 174 patients (56%) with CD4 count below 500 cells/mm³. [6]

Table 1. Characteristics of patients

Characteristics	Patients
Male	164(51.5)
Female	151(48.5)
Age (years) (n = 318)	
Interval	18-65
Mean	37 $\pm$ 12
18-25	22(6.9%)
26-35	129(40.6%)
36-45	107(33.6%)
46-55	48(15.1%)
56-65	12(3.8%)
Cd4 range	4-1591
Median cd4	560 cells/mm ³
WHO Clinical stages	
Stage I & II	295(92.5%)
Stage III & IV	23(7.5%)

DISCUSSION

The aim of this work was to determine the clinical and immunological failure rate at treatment in ART center King Koti, Hyderabad. The data collected from ART programme clinic provided evidence supporting that the first line therapy was effective in HIV infected patients attending the clinic. In India CD4 testing is available in all ART sites therefore immunological criteria are widely used to determine treatment failure. The survival analysis was carried out using CD4 counts stratification and the results showed that patients with advanced disease had probability of less survival as compared to those with ART initiation at CD4 counts of >100 cells/ μ l.

The optimal response to ART therapy is indicated by a median rise of CD4 count of 50 cells/ μ l at the end of 6 months or 100 cells/ μ l at one year of treatment. The studies conducted in different countries have documented different levels of rise in CD4 counts after the treatment. Our results on rise in CD4 counts are similar to that

observed in other studies in India as well as in other countries. [7-10]

Though overall immunological response was satisfactory, three patients did not show increase in CD4 cell count at 6 months and one year follow up. Viral load assays were not performed at scheduled follow up visits. So it was not clear whether the patients had suboptimal response to antiretroviral therapy or virological failure. In another study in Kenyan [11] also found that immunological and clinical failure had poor prediction of virological failure. The study showed the sensitivity of immunological and clinical failure to detect viral failure was 36.4%, specificity was 83.5% and the positive-predictive value was 12.3%. In this study the sensitivity was studied for each individual criteria which varied between 20 to 91%, specificity was between 29 to 87% and positive predictive value was 46 to 59% which was higher. In a study Natarajan Kandasamy [12,13] CD4 falling more than 50% criteria can alone be used to screen viral load for treatment failure. Stress on adherence for the whole duration of HAART rather than last 6 months may improve the immunological criteria sensitivity.

In another study in Mbeya Region, Tanzania Prevalence of immunological treatment failure was high (48.2%) among HIV-infected patients attending Care and Treatment Clinics (CTCs) in two hospitals. Increased age, being patient from District hospital, baseline CD4 cell values of ≥ 350 cells/ μ l, severe anemia (hemoglobin count <8 g/dL), longer duration from HIV infection diagnosis to ART initiation and AZT-based regimen were the significant predictors of immunological failure. [14]

Patients with IF were more likely to be early age adults, females, late presenters for HIV care, and have a low (<200 cells/mm³) baseline CD4 count and history of HIV testing before diagnosis. Very few patients were shifted to second-line ART drugs despite the high prevalence of CF and/or IF. [15]

CONCLUSION

The immunological failure rate of first-line antiretroviral treatment of patients on treatment in ART center King Koti is estimated at 7.5% for the year 2017 and 18.

REFERENCES

1. India HIV estimations 2017: Fact sheets, (<http://naco.gov.in/surveillance-epidemiology-0>)
2. Yeni P. Medical care of people infected with HIV. Paris: The French documentation. 2010 Sep.
3. Delfraissy, J.F. (2006) Therapeutic management of HIV-infected persons. Report 2004. Medicine-Sciences, Flammarion, Paris, France.
4. Morlat, P. (2013) Medical Management of People Living with HIV: Recommendations of the Expert Group. Under the aegis of CNS and ANRS, Rap-ports.
5. Kamangu NE, Chatte A, Susin F, Boreux R, Kalala LR, Mvumbi LG, De Mol P, Vaira D, Hayette MP. Genetic Diversity and Antiretroviral Drug Resistance among Drug-Naïve HIV Type 1 Infected Patients attending Clinics in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo. *Journal of HIV and AIDS*. 2015 ;1(1).
6. Kamangu NE, Bulanda IB, Bongenia IB, Botomwito TH, Mvumbi LG, De Mol P, Vaira D, Hayette MP, Kalala LR. Virological profile of patients infected with HIV starting antiretroviral treatment in Kinshasa. *Open Access Library Journal*. 2015;2(06):1.
7. Sharma SK, Dhooria S, Prasad KT, George N, Ranjan S, Gupta D, Sreenivas V, Kadhiraavan T, Miglani S, Sinha S, Wig N. Outcomes of antiretroviral therapy in a northern Indian urban clinic. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2010;88:222-6.
8. Bachani D, Garg R, Rewari BB, Hegg L, Rajasekaran S, Deshpande A, Emmanuel KV, Chan P, Sujatha Rao K. Two-year treatment outcomes of patients enrolled in India's national first-line antiretroviral therapy programme. *National Medical Journal of India*. 2010;23(1):7.
9. Landman R, Schiemann R, Thiam S, Vray M, Canestri A, Mboup S, Kane CT, Delaporte E, Sow PS, Faye MA, Gueye M. Once-a-day highly active antiretroviral therapy in treatment-naïve HIV-1-infected adults in Senegal. *Aids*. 2003;17(7):1017-22.
10. Zhou HY, Zheng YH, He Y, Chen Z, Liu M, Yin W, Liu C. Evaluation of a 6-year highly active antiretroviral therapy in Chinese HIV-1-infected patients. *Intervirology*. 2010;53(4):240-6.
11. Munderi P, van Praag E, Vella S. Safe and effective use of antiretroviral treatments in adults with particular references to resource limited settings.
12. Ferreyra C, Yun O, Eisenberg N, Alonso E, Khamadi AS, Mwau M, Mugendi MK, Alvarez A, Velilla E, Flevaud L, Arnedo M. Evaluation of clinical and immunological markers for predicting virological failure in a HIV/AIDS treatment cohort in Busia, Kenya. *PloS one*. 2012;7(11):e49834.
13. Kandasamy N, Radhakrishnan V, Subramanian A, Narayanan R, Muthalif MK, Narayanan N, Arunachalam R, Arumugam M. A study of people living with hiv-aids [plha] on first line highly active anti-retroviral therapy [haart] with immunological failure. *Journal of evolution of medical and dental sciences-jemds*. 2016;5(56):3872-6.
14. Kamugisha E, Chomboko CL, Kabyemera RM and Kidenya BR. (2018). Prevalence and Predictors of Immunological Treatment Failure among HIV Infected Adults on the First-line Antiretroviral Therapy in Mbeya Region Tanzania. *M J HIV*. 3(1): 017
15. Gesesew HA, Ward P, Woldemichael K, Mwanri L. Immunological failure in HIV-infected adults from 2003 to 2015 in Southwest Ethiopia: a retrospective cohort study. *BMJ open*. 2018;8(8):e017413.

How to cite this article: Pandharpurkar D, Krishna G, Begum GR et.al. Estimation of clinical, and immunological failure of first line antiretroviral treatment in King Koti ART centre, Hyderabad, Telangana. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(5):67-70.
